

Tsallis Entropy and a Conservation of Energy Scheme Part 2

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In Part I, we proposed defining a generalized probability $G(f(e_i))$ consistent with $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $G(f(e_1))G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3))G(f(e_4))$ (time reversal) such that: $d \ln G(f) = f^{-q} df$. This, in turn, led to the function: $\ln_q(f) = \{ f^{(1-q)} - 1 \} / (1-q)$ defined in (1). For $q=1$, $\ln_q(f)=\ln(f)$. Furthermore, $H_q =$ Tsallis entropy is defined in (1) as: $\sum_i f_i^q \ln_q(f_i)$. In other words, the $f_i \ln(f_i)$ Shannon's term is now associated with a $f_i \rightarrow f_i^q$ and $\ln(f_i) \rightarrow \ln_q(f_i)$. Thus, in the scheme of (1), it is no longer an average (in the simple $f(e_i)$ sense) of $\ln_q(f_i)$ for the Tsallis case. Furthermore, even though $f_i \rightarrow f_i^q$, and $d \ln(G) = f_i^{-q} df_i$, G is not linked in any simple manner to f_i^q , which is fine. We suggest here that one may interpret f_i^q in the Tsallis entropy equation of (1) as having a physical interpretation. In particular, instead of $f(e_i)$ describing the probability for an e_i to take part in an interaction, it may be the case that the physical presence of an e_i is not sufficient for a reaction to occur. It may take on average q tries before the interaction actually occurs. Alternatively, it may take on average the presence of q particles with e_i in order for one to react.

This would then account for $f(e_i)^q$ instead of $f(e_i)$. Here, each of the tries are independent. Once a reaction occurs, $G(f(e_i))$ then describes the specific probability. Thus, two generalizations of the Shannon's approach occur, one for f_i and the other for $\ln(f_i)$.

We compare this interpretation with a different physical scenario using Tsallis entropy formulated in a different mathematical manner in (2). In particular, instead of having a volume V divided into compartments of size V_0 , with the equal possibility of a particle being in a compartment, rather each compartment may hold up to q particles. The approach of (2) is that only one particle may be the correct one. Furthermore, it may be that none of the particles in a compartment are correct. This last scenario leads to a geometric series which then leads to Tsallis entropy again, but without $\ln_q(f_i)$ or f_i^q appearing. In other words, both the approaches of (1) and (2) lead to the same Tsallis entropy, but use different formalisms. Here, we consider the differences between the two schemes.

Generalization of the In Function from Part I

In Part I, we considered generalizing the \ln function based on a physical scheme, namely:

$$E_1+E_2 = E_3+E_4 \text{ (elastic interactions) } ((1a)) \text{ and } f(e_1) f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) ((1b))$$

As noted in Part I, the standard procedure is to take \ln of ((1b)) and equate it with ((1a)) multiplied by a constant. It was also argued in Part I, that instead of taking \ln of ((1b)), one could take the differential and then divide by the function itself to obtain:

$$df(e_i)/f(e_i) \quad ((2)) \text{ terms}$$

((2)) readily integrates to the \ln function, but in more complicated situations, such as the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, one has:

$$G(f(e1)) G(f(e2)) = G(f(e3)) G(f(e4)) \quad ((3))$$

In such a case, $d \ln G$ when integrated does not lead to $\ln(f(e_i))$. In particular, we applied this approach to the case:

$$d \ln(G(f_i)) = f_i^{\text{power } -q} df_i \quad ((4b)) \text{ to obtain } \ln_q(f) = \{ f_i^{\text{power } (1-q) - 1} \} / (1-q) \quad ((4b))$$

For $q=1$, $\ln_q(f) = \ln(f)$. The question then becomes: What is the entropy using this new $\ln(G)$?

In (1), the entropy (Tsallis entropy) is formally given as:

$$S_{\text{Tsallis}} = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } f_i^{\text{power } q} \ln_q(f_i) \quad ((5))$$

For $q=1$, $f_i^{\text{power } q} \rightarrow f_i$ and $\ln_q(f_i) \rightarrow \ln(f_i)$.

Does one still have the sense of an average of information as in the Shannon's case: $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } f_i \ln(f_i)$? Now, $\ln_q(f_i) = \ln(G(f_i))$, but the weighting probability in the scheme of (1) is $f_i^{\text{power } q}$. The question then arises: What is the physical meaning of $f_i^{\text{power } q}$? It seems to suggest that instead of using $f(e_i) = f_i$ as the probability weight for a $G(f(e_i))$, one uses instead a product $f_i^{\text{power } q}$ which has the interpretation of q independent AND situation f_i appearances. Thus, one does not have the Shannon's (Maxwell-Boltzmann's) scenario of $f(e_i)$ representing the probability of an e_i interacting in a two body collision. There is no issue of having a complicated $G(f(e_i))$ describing the interaction, but now one has an unusual $f_i^{\text{power } q}$ weight for e_i to be part of the interaction. In other words, the reaction is suppressed by $f_i^{\text{power } q}$ if $q > 1$.

There is a possible physical interpretation. In the usual Maxwell-Boltzmann scenario, the probability for an e_i to interact is given by $f(e_i)$, the probability for an e_i to be present at x . One might argue, however, on physical grounds, that having a particle with e_i present is not enough to guarantee a successful interaction. Sometimes specific interactions simply do not occur even if a particle with e_i is present. In particular, one might argue that it takes q independent tries before an interaction occurs. Then, the probability for an interaction with e_i is:

$$f(e_i)^{\text{power } q} \quad ((6))$$

The specifics of the interaction conserving energy are, however, specifically described by $G(f(e_i))$ such that $\ln(G(f(e_i))) = \ln_q(f(e_i))$, but a $f(e_i)^{\text{power } q}$ is the probability weight because not all e_i interact even if they are present.

We suggest that this physical interpretation follows from the mathematical approach given in (1).

In (2), a somewhat similar physical scenario is given, but it is not linked to two body scattering and the mathematical formulation differs from that of (1). In the end, however, the same expression for Tsallis entropy is obtained. We consider this approach in the next section.

Approach of (2) and Tsallis Entropy

In (2), it is argued that a box of volume V divided into compartments of size V_0 is associated with a Shannon's entropy linked to the constant probability V_0/V of finding a particle in any compartment. This scenario is then generalized to allow for up to q particles in each compartment with the stipulation that only one particle may be the "correct" particle. It is possible, however, that no particle is the correct one in the box and this is the probability/average with which (2) is concerned.

Thus, (2) defines a $\langle p^{q-1} \rangle$ average. It is defined as the average "probability to register a false particle.. per one false particle.

$$(1-p)/(1-q) \sum_{r=1}^{q-1} p^r \quad ((7))$$

The sum only goes to $q-1$ because the maximum number of failures is $q-1$ and the last particle must be correct. The sum starts at $r=1$ because one must register at least one false particle in an expression defining the probability to find a false particle. $|1-q|$ in the denominator is the maximum number of false particles one may find. $(1-p)$ is the probability of not finding a particle. Thus, ((7)) is the average of not finding a correct particle in a compartment.

As a result, the physical scenario of (2) is a somewhat different scenario than that given above as an interpretation of the formalism of (1). Nevertheless, ((7)), when summed over r for a geometric series yields:

$$p/(q-1) (\{p^{q-1} - 1\}) \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is the standard term in an expression for Tsallis entropy given in (3), namely:

$$S_{\text{Tsallis}} = 1/(q-1) (1 - \sum p_i^q) \quad ((9))$$

((9)) is identical to H_q defined in (1) i.e. $\sum_i p_i^q \ln_q(p_i)$ ((10)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we use the formalism of Part I which defines Tsallis entropy as $\sum_i p_i^q \ln_q(p_i)$ and try to describe this expression in terms of physical elastic scattering. In Part I, we already suggested that for: $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $G(f(e_1)) G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3)) G(f(e_4))$, the Tsallis scenario is consistent with $d \ln(G(f)) = f^{-q} df$. Here, we suggest that f_i^q (instead of f_i in the Shannon case) suggests the presence of a particle with energy e_i is not

sufficient to guarantee a reaction. In fact, on average q attempts must occur for one successful e_i reaction, ignoring further possible restrictions due to $G(f(e_i))$. It is as if a particle with e_i must try q times before even initiating a reaction. Thus, we argue that the formalism of (1) may be applied to an elastic scattering scenario in which the reaction itself follows $d \ln G(f) = f^{-q} df$, where $G(f)$ is the generalized probability describing the reaction itself (time reversal), while f^{-q} means that one can only consider a reaction after q independent tries for which an e_i particle is present.

In (2), a different math scheme and physical interpretation is given to obtain the same Tsallis entropy. In this case, it is assumed that one has a volume broken into equal compartments, but that each may hold up to q particles. Only one particle may be the correct one. One may, however, have cases in which there is no correct particle in a box. The average probability for this leads to a geometric series which, when summed, yields a correct summand for Tsallis entropy when the expression given in (3) (and not (1)) is used. (Overall, of course the two expressions are identical.)

References

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